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The effect of memory capacity on the foraging efficiency of primates

by

Sarah Emmen Riedel
10981683

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Assessor:
Dr. K.R.L. Janmaat

Examiner:
Dr. Ir. E.E. van Loon

Institute for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Dynamics

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The ecological intelligence hypothesis proposes that factors of diet, such as the food type eaten and its spatiotemporal food distribution in the habitat, are the primary selective force behind the evolution of intelligent behaviour. Spatial memory is thought to be an important cognitive ability that is adapted to forage more efficiently. In this study, an Agent-Based Model (ABM) was created to test the effect of spatial memory capacity on the foraging efficiency of chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*). Research has shown that chimpanzees use long-term spatial memory to relocate fruit-bearing trees in their complex habitat. However, it is not clear yet how the memory capacity, including both its size (how many items can be remembered) and retention (how long items can be remembered), contributes to foraging efficiency. The foraging efficiency is here defined as the amount of food eaten during ten days of travelling. Based on experiments of the ABM, it appeared that both memory size and retention did not influence the foraging efficiency of the agent. Thus, memory capacity did not affect the foraging efficiency of chimpanzees, and no evidence is provided for the ecological intelligence hypothesis. The current ABM is a good starting point to study how spatial memory could be beneficial for the fitness of individuals. Hence it is recommended to use the ABM of this study as a prototype and update it to a more accurate and enhanced model, using the proposed improvements.

Keywords: memory capacity, foraging efficiency, Agent-Based Model, ecological intelligence hypothesis, chimpanzees, *Pan troglodytes*

Introduction

What makes us human? What distinguishes humans from other animal species? Many propositions have been made on these universal and fundamental questions. In the last decades, research focusses on brain size and how this could be related to the exceptional cognitive abilities of humans. Research has shown that the human brain is much larger than expected for a primate body size (Jerison, 1973; Martin, 1981; Marino, 1998). However, it has been proposed that the cellular composition of the human brain is not unique but instead is a linearly scaled-up primate brain (Herculano-Houzel, 2009). When looking at the number of neurons and non-neuronal cells in the brain of different mammals from various orders, the human brain is not an outlier of the general rule anymore but has the expected number of neuronal and non-neuronal cells for a primate brain of its size. This could mean that humans do not have unique cognitive abilities but differ from other species by combining and extending certain abilities (Herculano-Houzel, 2009; Marino et al., 2007). Behavioural complexity is the result of neural function, which is determined by the number of neurons and their relative abundance in different parts of the brain, specific to a species (Williams and Herrup, 1988; Roth and Dicke 2005). Many other studies use different measurements of brain size to link to cognitive abilities. For example, absolute brain size (Reader and Laland, 2002; Deaner et al., 2007; Kotrschal et al., 2014), relative brain size to body size (Sol et al., 2005), and the size of the neocortex (Byrne and Corp, 2004; Shultz and Dunbar, 2010) are all found to be related to cognitive abilities.

So, there is a large body of evidence that humans have enlarged brains and that brain size (regardless of its measurement) is related to cognitive functioning. However, it remains unclear why differences in cognitive abilities emerge. Understanding the driving forces that have shaped human and primate intelligence in the past will provide more insight into what exactly distinguishes humans from other animal species today. Two main hypotheses explain the evolution of primate cognition, the social intelligence hypothesis and the ecological intelligence hypothesis. The social intelligence hypothesis states that social complexity is the main selective force behind the evolution of enlarged brains, and consequently, intelligence (Jolly, 1966; Humphry, 1976). On the other side, the ecological intelligence hypothesis proposes that factors of the diet are the primary force shaping intelligent behaviour (Milton, 1981; Sol, 2009; Rosati, 2017). These factors include the food type eaten and the difficulty of locating it in the habitat due to its distribution or density.

The social intelligence hypothesis is based on the findings that primates with relatively large brains show remarkably complex social interactions (Goodall, 1986; Romero et al., 2011). Better cognitive functioning could result from social challenges, including recognising third-party relationships and anticipating the behaviour of others. This is supported by studies that show a relationship between these advanced social behaviours and other social complexity measures and brain size (Reader and Laland, 2002; Shultz and Dondorp, 2007; Ashton et al., 2018). However, the social intelligence hypothesis on its own cannot explain the origins of intelligence. A larger brain requires more energy intake to be able to support it, especially considering that brain tissue is the most metabolically expensive tissue compared to all other tissues in mammals (Allman, 1999). Although evidence shows that sociality has a positive impact on fitness (Silk et al., 2003), the social intelligence hypothesis does not provide a direct mechanism that could compensate for the costs of having a large brain. Besides, brain size relative to body mass has also been related to ecology (Sol et al., 2005), and not only to sociality. Some studies even show that dietary niche is a predictor of brain size and social complexity not within the same study (MacLean et al., 2009; DeCasien et al., 2017). These findings are in contrast with views that the social intelligence hypothesis shapes general cognitive mechanisms.

The social and ecological intelligence hypotheses are not necessarily mutually exclusive. Both can explain variation in cognition, but each might be relevant in distinct cognitive domains and shape different cognitive systems (Rosati, 2017). As the ecological intelligence hypothesis proposes, the variation in ecology can also explain how differences in brain size and cognitive abilities emerge (Milton, 1981; Sol, 2009). When searching for food, foragers face various challenges, such as competition for the same food resources (Barange et al., 2005) and the availability of the food resources (Loarie et al., 2009). To cope with a certain level of complexity in the environment, a certain level of cognitive functioning is necessary. Research shows that the variation in cognitive skills used during food acquisition can be explained by the variation found in ecology (Rosati, 2017). One such cognitive skill used for foraging is the use of spatial memory.

Many animal species are known to use spatial memory as a strategy to locate food resources, among which bees (Menzel et al., 2005), elephants (Presotto et al., 2019), mangabeys (Janmaat et al., 2006), baboons (Pochron, 2001; Noser and Byrne, 2007), and chimpanzees (Normand and Boesch, 2009; Janmaat et al., 2013a). The ability to remember locations of food resources and to navigate efficiently between them is expressed in complex foraging behaviour. This behaviour could be adaptive since species that live in ecologically harsh conditions, in which food is difficult to find by chance, are found to perform better in spatial memory tasks (Rosati, 2017; Croston et al., 2015). An evident example is that frugivore primates have larger brains and perform better on spatial memory tests than folivore primates (Clutton-Brock and Harvey, 1980; MacLean et al., 2009; Rosati et al., 2014). Fruit trees are ephemeral and patchily distributed, whereas leaves are more homogeneous with regard to their distribution and availability. Therefore, frugivore primates are required to rely more on spatial memory to find food. An observational study comparing foraging efficiency within species found that grey-cheeked mangabeys (*Lophocebus albigena johnstonii*) forage less efficient in areas of which they have no long-term spatial memory (Janmaat and Chancellor, 2010). However, it is still unclear what aspects of spatial memory exactly improve fitness within species. In particular, what information is remembered to improve foraging efficiency?

This study will focus on chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*) and how spatial memory influences their foraging efficiency. Chimpanzees live in a complex rainforest environment, especially considering that they are frugivores (Wrangham et al., 1998). Despite the high abundance of plant species in the tropical rainforest that chimpanzees feed on (Janmaat et al., 2016), the fruiting of tropical fruit trees is characterised by spatiotemporal fluctuations. Size, duration, and frequency of fruiting peaks differ between tree species and within species, resulting in periods of abundance and scarcity (van Schaik et al., 1993; Chapman et al., 1999; Chapman et al., 2005). In times of scarcity, the percentage of trees bearing ripe fruit can drop to 0.3%, and the encounter rate can be one ripe fruit-bearing tree every 1,730 m (Janmaat et al., 2016), keeping in mind that on average chimpanzees travel 2,400 m every day (Doran, 1997; Bates and Byrne, 2009).

The complex but still somewhat predictable reproduction patterns of fruit trees in the tropical rainforest challenge chimpanzees in their daily search and place a premium on those individuals that can employ cognitive abilities that facilitate fruit finding. In contrast to completely ordered or random food distributions, the use of memory in this tropical forest environment is highly valuable for efficient foraging and could contribute to fitness (Sambrook and Whiten, 1997; Fagan et al., 2013). The distribution of ripe fruits in the rainforest resulting from the varying reproduction patterns between and within the fruit tree species is predictable without perfect knowledge. The intermediate complexity of this predictability is thought to be an important selective force in the development of advanced cognitive abilities of primates (Milton, 1981). Within tropical fruit tree species, 64% bears fruit synchronously (Chapman et al., 1999). Chimpanzees and grey-cheeked mangabeys are found to use this synchronous property of fruit trees to find food while foraging (Janmaat et al., 2012; Janmaat et al., 2013b).

Research has shown that chimpanzees have a highly accurate memory for food locations. This is supported by studies showing that chimpanzees travel relatively straight to a potential feeding tree and do so from many different directions (Normand and Boesch, 2009; Janmaat et al., 2013a). This is emphasised by a significant change in direction in the relatively straight routes, called changing points, prior to the linear travel and at the feeding tree. These changing points indicate that the tree was the goal that the chimpanzee was heading to (Janmaat et al., 2013a; Ban et al., 2014; Ban et al., 2016). Changing points are associated with biologically relevant goals, such as feeding trees (Byrne et al., 2009). Thus, a changing point followed by a linear travel to a feeding tree, and after which they continue in another direction, suggests that chimpanzees plan where to go and remember the precise location of the tree. Besides food locations, chimpanzees also seem to know the distance to the goal tree as they decelerate their travel speed when nearing their goal (Normand and Boesch, 2009). Knowledge of the tree locations and the distance to food resources is shown to increase the foraging efficiency significantly (Janson, 2019).

Janmaat et al. (2013a) studied which properties of fruit trees are considered by chimpanzees during foraging. It was found that chimpanzees fed in and monitored trees with larger tree trunks compared to control trees. Trunk size was determined by measuring the diameter of the trunk at breast height (DBH), 1.2 m above the ground. DBH is a consistently accurate method to estimate the food production of fruit trees (Chapman et al., 1992). Of the monitored trees, 13% preceded a goal-directed approach, meaning that the tree was associated with a changing point in their travel route but did not bear fruit. Janmaat et al. (2013a) tested what factors increased the probability that a monitored tree was preceded by a goal-directed approach. Crown size, as a measurement for potential fruit production, increased the probability of a goal-directed approach, but the current amount of food present at a tree did not affect the probability that a monitored tree was preceded by a goal-directed approach. These results indicate that chimpanzees have not only a long-term memory for the location of fruit trees but also the size or potential food production.

Ban et al. (2014) measured the distance travelled to revisited trees as a measure of prospective memory, using the same observational data. Chimpanzees travelled further for trees with a larger amount of food. This was unlikely explained by the use of sensory cues since crown size did not influence the approach distance. Thus, chimpanzees might have a 'what-where-when' memory as they can anticipate the amount of fruit present at a tree. However, it is unclear how well chimpanzees remember when a tree produces fruit since they travel to fruit trees that do not bear fruit. However, visiting an empty tree does not necessarily mean that the memory was incorrect. If a person visits a restaurant that they used to eat at half a year ago, they may find it closed. It does not mean that the memory of this person was incorrect, but it could mean that the anticipation was not correct. Further, monitoring could be a necessary strategy to find newly produced fruit.

Propositions on how long information stays in the spatial memory vary widely. Predictions can be made by either observing the revisit behaviour of animals in their natural habitat or by considering regeneration rates of food sources. Revisits occur on average within five days, which is more often than expected by chance (Normand et al., 2009). This indicates that chimpanzees probably have a retention of at least five days. However, in the study of Ban et al. (2014), chimpanzees revisited trees up to 26

days after the previous visit. In addition, chimpanzees fed on trees with fruit production intervals ranging from two months to up to three years (Janmaat et al., 2013a). Hence, the effective memory window is expected to be within this range. Additionally, the regrowth times and intervals between fruiting periods can be many months (Janmaat et al., 2016). It may be beneficial to still remember the tree's location so that the primate can monitor these trees. It could be argued that the more is remembered, the better the foragers would be able to predict the fruit peaks of individual trees or species. This can be beneficial for foraging efficiency, but then it is assumed that the chimpanzees have perfect memory. The more information is acquired, the more likely that two separate memories will interact or confound (Kane and Engle, 2000). An adult female chimpanzee is estimated to encounter 47,318 food trees during their lifetime, so the total number of potential food trees is enormous. Therefore, forgetting is an important mechanism to avoid interference of memories (Fagan et al., 2013). By forgetting less relevant information, memory capacity can remain smaller. This seems to be true as chimpanzees tend to visit larger trees.

Having a more precise memory ('what-where-when' compared to 'where' memory) is more beneficial for foraging efficiency (Janson, 2019), but animals have limited capacity for processing and storing information accurately over the long term. Hence a possible trade-off exists between the quality and quantity of memory. If everything is remembered, more mistakes will be made due to interference. On the other side, if few are remembered, the memory could be of higher quality. This study aims to determine how memory capacity, both size and retention, influence the foraging efficiency of chimpanzees. By knowing the effects of memory size and retention on the foraging efficiency, implications can be made about the trade-off between the quality and quantity of spatial memory and about the adaptive value of enhanced spatial memory. This will provide more insight into the ecological intelligence hypothesis.

It is difficult to study memory capacity and its adaptive traits in a complex environment with empirical research. It has been done, but it is challenging to exclude confounding factors (Janmaat and Chancellor, 2010). Hence an Agent-Based Model (ABM) will be created to study the memory capacity of chimpanzees. ABMs model the world using agents, an environment, and a description of the interactions between those. This way, a complex system-level effect can be studied by implementing more simple local interactions. Using an ABM, the complex environment of chimpanzees can be completely controlled, and confounding factors can be avoided. Chimpanzees tend to stay in their territories seasonally (Herbinger et al., 2001) and forage alone during fruit scarce periods (Wrangham, 1977). This makes chimpanzees appropriate study subjects for ABMs. Empirical data of a chimpanzee group in the Taï National Park, Côte d'Ivoire, will be used to recreate the natural habitat of the chimpanzees in the ABM.

Methods

An ABM was created in R version 3.6.3 to investigate the effect of memory capacity on the foraging efficiency of chimpanzees in the Taï National Park, Côte d'Ivoire. For a detailed model description following the Overview, Design concepts, and Details (ODD) protocol, see appendix A. Here only the key concepts are described. The ABM consisted of two main components, an agent and an environment. The agent in this model was a single chimpanzee (henceforth denoted as agent) that could forage through the environment. The artificially created environment consisted of trees that differed in properties. The fruit, nuts, or young leaves on the trees were food resources for the agent. The movement of the agent and the interactions between the agent and the environment are described in the model.

The model environment recreated the natural environment of the Taï chimpanzees. It constituted a square area of 26.5 km² with a core area of 17.8 km² in the centre, similar to the territory and core area size of the chimpanzee group in the Taï rainforest (Janmaat et al., 2013a). The model environment contained trees of fifteen different species, among which abundant and rare species (Normand, 2009). These trees were all potential food resources for the agent and were described by five key variables:

Figure 1. The model environment of the Agent-Based Model. A. The 26.5 km² environment contains 20,072 food resources (trees) for the agent. Each point in the area represents one tree. The size represents the DBH in meters and the colour represents the food index. The red striped line is the border between the 17.8 km² core area in the centre and the periphery of the range area. The small black square is the zoomed area shown on the left side (B).

density, location, maximum detection distance (MDD), DBH, and food index. The values of these five key variables depended on the species of the tree and were based on empirical data derived from different studies in the Taï National Park, including phenological data (Anderson et al., 2005; Janmaat et al., 2013a), chimpanzee behaviour and botanical map of core area data (Janmaat et al., 2013a), and additional density data (Goné Bi, 2007). Determining the values of the key variables for individual trees in the model environment using the empirical data involved two main steps: (1) determining the probability distributions or descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum) of the key variables of each tree species based on observational data in Taï National Park, and (2) applying these distributions or parameters to generate random samples of each key variable of each species. This way, each tree in the model environment was assigned a location, MDD, DBH, and food index. For detailed information on how the empirical data was used to assign values for the different key variables to the individual trees, see appendix B.

The density of each tree species determined how many trees of a species were present in the model environment. Each tree was assigned a random location while avoiding unrealistic short distances between trees or overlap among trees. The MDD determined from which distance a tree could be noticed by the agent. At last, the DBH and food index together determined how much food was available at each tree. The DBH represented the tree's maximum potential food production (Chapman et al., 1992) and the food index determined what part of this maximum potential food production was present. The food index ranks 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 corresponded to 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of the maximum potential food production of the tree. See figure 1 for a depiction of the model environment.

The agent was characterised by its memory, location, and movement. The memory stored information about the trees in the model environment. It could differ in size (the number of trees that could be remembered) and retention interval (the time period over which the trees could be remembered). The following attributes were stored for all trees in the memory: location, DBH, whether food was present,

and when the tree was last seen by the agent. Each memory of a tree also had an associated strength. The memory strength of trees that were expected to have food was 1.5 times stronger than memories of trees that were expected to be empty. Additionally, the memory strength was inversely proportional to the distance in time that the tree was last seen by the agent; the longer ago the tree was seen, the weaker the memory strength. The memory strength determined which tree had to be forgotten in order to create memory space for a new tree memory. The trees that had the weakest memory strength were forgotten first. A new tree was added to the memory when the agent was within the MDD of a tree for which the agent did not have a memory yet.

At each location of the agent, a sequence of steps was executed. First, it was checked whether the agent could notice a tree from its current location by checking whether the agent was within the MDD of a tree. If so, the time (measured in ticks) was stored when the tree was seen. If the tree was not stored in the memory yet, it was added to the memory. Then it was checked for all trees in the agent's memory whether they were last seen within the retention interval. Otherwise, the tree was forgotten and removed from the memory. After that, the agent would visit a tree when its current position was within a two-meter distance of a tree. In which case the agent would consume all food available at that tree. The DBH of the visited tree and the amount of food eaten were recorded in an output file to determine the foraging efficiency. At last, a new direction was determined in which the agent would move two meters. Since the agent moved with a constant speed, the temporal and spatial units were both represented by the same unit, a tick.

To determine at every tick in which direction the agent chose to travel, the agent used the additive-gravity rule. The additive-gravity rule assumes that every goal of an individual has an attraction that is proportional to a certain value and is inversely proportional to the distance from the individual (Janson, 2014). The attraction to a goal can be represented as a vector in the direction of the goal. The summed vector will point in the direction the individual moves and is calculated for each step an individual takes. Together with the 3-step look-ahead rule, the additive-gravity rule provided frequent significant positive correlations between observed and predicted routes of primates (Janson, 2014). The 3-step look-ahead rule contemplates many possible paths with three consecutive goals and chooses the shortest path. The individual will move to the first goal of the three. The additive-gravity rule and the 3-step look-ahead rule differ in that by using the additive-gravity rule, the forager does not plan where to go but is guided by the gravity of the goals. The 3-step look-ahead rule is unnecessarily cognitive complex and furthermore assumes that all resources are equally valued by the forager (Janson, 2014). By using the additive-gravity rule, agents were attracted to highly valuable goals or clusters of goals. This is also consistent with observations in the wild that show that chimpanzees travelled further for highly valued (large or more productive) trees (Ban et al., 2014; Janson, 2014). Besides, it allows for adjusting routes along the way to trees to which the chimpanzees were not planning to go initially.

In this model, the additive-gravity rule was applied for all the trees in the memory at each tick. The attraction towards each tree depended on the DBH, the distance towards the tree, whether it was located in the core area or the periphery (figure 1), and whether food was present. The larger the tree and the shorter the distance, the greater the attraction towards the tree. If the tree was located in the core area, the attraction was increased by 50%. The greater attraction towards the core area was added so the agent would stay within the territory. An increase of 50% resulted in routes of the agent in the model that were visually similar to those of wild chimpanzees in their territory observed in Tai National Park (Janmaat et al., 2013a). When the tree did not bear fruit, the tree was excluded from the summation of all the vectors to prevent attraction towards empty trees. The magnitude of the attraction determined the length of the vector in the direction of the tree. The summed vector pointed in the direction the agent would move. A visualisation of the additive-gravity rule is depicted in figure 2. If the summed vector did not have a magnitude and thus no direction, then the agent would turn into a random direction between 40 degrees to the right and 40 degrees to the left.

Figure 2. The basic principle of the additive-gravity rule. Towards each tree in the memory, an attraction vector is created from the agent (red point) to the trees (green). The length of the vector depends on the magnitude of the attraction (black arrows), which is affected by the DBH of the tree and the distance to the tree. Trees in the core area (dark green background) are 1.5 time more attractive than tree in the periphery (light green background). The summed vector points into the direction the agent will travel (red striped arrow).

Simulations

The agent started each simulation in the centre of the model environment. One simulation represented ten days of foraging to get stable and thus reliable results (see figure A2 in appendix A). Chimpanzees travel on average 2.4 km in one day (Doran, 1997; Bates and Byrne, 2009). Because the step length in this model was 2 m, ten days of travelling equalled 12,000 ticks. The memory size was set to 1000, 1500, or 2000 trees. When the memory size was smaller than 1000 trees, the agent's movement was random and unnatural. This happened because the agent would have seen or visited all the trees stored in the memory within the ten days of travelling. All the trees would have been depleted by the agent, leaving no trees in the agent's memory to attract the agent. If the memory size contained 1000 trees or more this would not happen within the ten days of travelling. With the resources available for this research, typically, a single model run with 2000 trees in memory would roughly take 8 hours to run. Hence the memory sizes chosen were between 1000 and 2000 trees. The retention interval was set to one month (30 days), two months (60 days), or one year (356 days), covering the expected effective memory window and the known revisit intervals of chimpanzees (Janmaat et al., 2013a; Ban et al., 2014). Accidentally, the retention interval was set to 356 days instead of 365 days to represent one year. The nine-day difference was not expected to make a major difference when interpreting the results; therefore, the simulations were not rerun.

Before a simulation was run, an initial memory was created for the agent containing a set of random trees from the model environment. The number of trees stored in the initial memory depended on the memory size. Because the chimpanzees do not have a perfect memory of when a tree bears fruits and often inspected empty trees (Janmaat et al., 2013a; Janmaat et al., 2013b), the agent did not have a perfect memory as well. In the behaviour data of Janmaat et al. (2013a), 39.1% of the visited trees did not bear fruit. The percentage of trees in the chimpanzee's memory that was not visited, although they had fruit, is impossible to measure. Therefore, the agent's memory about whether food was present or absent was for 39.1% of the trees set to be incorrect. So, for 39.1% of the trees in the agent's memory, it was set to have no food or have food although they had food or no food respectively in the model environment. For each tree in the initial memory, it was also determined how long ago the tree was last seen. This was randomly assigned, ranging from 0 ticks to the number of ticks equal to the retention interval of the agent.

During each simulation, three measurements for the foraging efficiency were obtained. (1) The total food intake (m) was the total amount of food consumed by the agent during one simulation. To calculate the food available at a tree, the DBH was used as a measurement of the maximum potential food production (Chapman et al., 1992) and the food index determined what percentage of this maximum potential production was present. Because the exact relationship between DBH (in m) and the biomass of fruit (in kg) is unknown (Ngomanda et al., 2014; Ouédraogo et al., 2020), the total food intake was not converted to biomass and hence measured in meters. (2) The summed DBH (m) of all visited trees was measured to exclude the effects of the randomly assigned food index values to the trees and the incorrect memories of food presence on foraging efficiency. Therefore, this measurement represented the foraging efficiency in this model if the memory of food presence had been completely correct and if all the visited trees had the maximal potential food production present. (3) The number of visited trees during one simulation was recorded to assess the contribution of memorising DBH (or potential food production) on the foraging efficiency when compared to summed DBH.

To study the effect of memory capacity on the foraging efficiency, the model was run nine times in the same environment but with varying memory sizes and retention intervals. The initial memories differed between these simulations because of the different memory sizes and retention intervals. To test the potential influence of the initial memory, the model was run an additional five times in the same environment. The memory size and retention interval were kept constant during these simulations. At last, to test for the effect caused by the environment, five simulations were run in five different environments while keeping the memory size and retention interval constant. The initial memories differed in these simulations because of the different environments. A total of 17 simulations were run, see table 1.

Table 1. Number of simulations run with different memory capacities in varying environments. To investigate the effect of memory capacity on foraging efficiency, the model was run nine times with varying memory sizes and retention intervals in one environment. To control for the variation caused by the initial memory, the model was run five times in the same environment. The model was also run in five different environments to control for variation caused by the environment.

Memory size (number of trees)		1000			1500			2000		
Retention interval (days)		30	60	356	30	60	356	30	60	356
Number of simulations run in each environment	A	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	B		5							
	C		1							
	D		1							
	E		1							

Data-analysis

To investigate the main effect of memory size and retention interval on the foraging efficiency, three two-way ANOVA tests were conducted after checking for the homogeneity of variance and normality of residuals. The first two-way ANOVA tested the effect of memory size and retention interval on the total food intake of the agent. The second two-way ANOVA tested the effect of memory size and retention interval on the summed DBH of all the visited trees, and the last two-way ANOVA tested the effect of memory size and retention interval on the number of trees visited by the agent. Only the nine simulations in the same environment with different memory sizes and retention intervals were included in these tests. A Tukey post-hoc test was performed when a significant main effect was found.

To control for variation caused by the initial memories, the mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation were calculated for the total food intake, summed DBH, and the number of visited trees of five the simulations in the same environment, and with the same memory size and retention interval. To control for the variation caused by the environment, the mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation were calculated for the total food intake, summed DBH, and the number of visited trees of five the simulations in different environments, but with the same memory size and retention interval.

Results

An example of a route travelled by an agent during one simulation is displayed in figure 3. No differences were found between the nine simulations in the total food intake when having different memory sizes ($F(1,2) = 0.325, p > 0.05$) and different retention intervals ($F(1,2) = 2.385, p > 0.05$). There was also no significant difference found between the summed DBH of the visited trees when having varying memory sizes ($F(1,2) = 0.281, p > 0.05$), but there was a difference found between the summed DBHs when having different retention intervals ($F(1,2) = 5.280, p = 0.059$). A Tukey post-hoc test revealed a trend in pairwise differences between the summed DBH when having a retention interval of 30 days and a retention interval of 60 days. The summed DBH of the visited trees was larger when the agent had a retention interval of 30 days compared to when the agent had a retention interval of 60 days (see figure 4). There was no significant difference found in the number of trees visited when the agent had different memory sizes ($F(1,2) = 0.340, p > 0.05$). The number of trees visited did differ significantly when having varying retention intervals ($F(1,2) = 6.528, p < 0.040$). A Tukey post-hoc test revealed significant pairwise differences between the number of trees visited when having a retention interval of 30 days and a retention interval of 60 days. The agent visited more trees when it had a retention interval of 30 days compared to when it had a retention interval of 60 days (see figure 4).

To control for the effect of the environment on the foraging efficiency, five simulations were run in five different environments while the agents had the same memory sizes and retention intervals. There were no large differences found between the variation within the total food intake, summed DBH, and number of trees (figure 5 and table 2). To control for the effect of the different initial memories, another five simulations were run in the same environment with the same memory sizes and retention intervals but different initial memories. Again, there were no large differences between the variation within the total food intake, summed DBH, and the number of trees (figure 6 and table 3). However, the variation within the number of trees is slightly smaller than the variation within total food intake and the summed DBH.

Figure 3. Route travelled during one simulation. A. The route travelled in the model environment by an agent during one simulation is shown in red. The points represent the food resources of the agent (trees). The size of the trees represents the DBH (m), as measurement of potential food production, and the colour represent the food index, which determines how much food of the maximal food production (DBH) is present. The small black square is the area that is zoomed in shown on the left side (B).

Figure 4. The effect of memory capacity on foraging efficiency. The (A) total food intake (m), (B) summed DBH (m) of the visited trees, and (C) the number of trees visited is shown when having different memory sizes and retention intervals.

Table 2. Variation within the foraging efficiency metrics when controlling for the model environment. The mean, standard deviation (SD), and coefficient of variation (CV) is shown for the total food intake, summed DBH, and number of trees visited.

	Mean	SD	CV
Total food intake	48.8	4.3	8.9
Sum DBH	185.9	18.6	10.0
Number of trees	226.4	18.8	8.3

Table 3. Variation within the foraging efficiency metrics when controlling for the initial memory of the agent. The mean, standard deviation (SD), and coefficient of variation (CV) is shown for the total food intake, summed DBH, and number of trees visited.

	Mean	SD	CV
Total food intake	45.2	4.8	10.7
Sum DBH	176.4	18.1	10.3
Number of trees	218.6	17.1	7.8

Figure 5. The effect of the model environment on foraging efficiency. The variation caused by foraging in five different environments is shown for (A) the total food intake, (B) the summed DBH of the visited trees, and (C) the number of trees visited.

Figure 6. The effect of the initial memory of the agent on foraging efficiency. The variation caused by five different initial memories is shown for (A) the total food intake, (B) the summed DBH of the visited trees, and (C) the number of trees visited.

Discussion

This study investigated by means of an ABM how memory capacity, both its size and retention, could influence the foraging efficiency of chimpanzees in the Taï National Park, Côte d'Ivoire. The ABM consisted of an environment that simulated the Taï chimpanzees' natural environment and an agent that foraged in this environment. The agent navigated using its memory which could vary in size and retention. The total food intake of the agent during one simulation was recorded as a measurement for foraging efficiency. The summed DBH of all visited trees during one simulation was also recorded. This measurement excluded the effect of the randomly assigned food indices to the trees that determined how much food was present of the maximum potential food production of a tree (DBH). It also excluded the effect of the incorrect memories of whether food was present at a tree. Thus, the summed DBH was a measurement for foraging efficiency if the agent's memory had been completely correct and if the maximum potential food production was present at all (visited) trees.

The statistical results showed that memory size did not affect the total food intake of the agent and the summed DBH of the visited trees. Memory retention did not influence the total food intake as well, but the summed DBH was larger when the agent had a retention interval of 30 days compared to when the agent had a retention interval of 60 days. This could mean that a shorter retention interval only increases the foraging efficiency if it is always correctly remembered how much food is available and if always the maximum potential amount of food is present. However, only one simulation was run per memory size and retention interval combination. When interpreting the results, the potential effects of the initial memory and the environment should be considered too.

To control for the effects of the environment on the foraging efficiency, several simulations were run in different environments while the agent had the same memory size and retention interval. The variation between the total food intake, summed DBH, and number of visited trees was similar (CV; table 2). However, the initial memories differed between these simulations because of the different environments. To control for the effect of the initial memories, several simulations were run in the same environment, while the agent had the same memory size and retention interval, but different initial memories. Again, the variation between the total food intake, summed DBH, and number of visited trees was similar (CV; table 3). Additionally, the variation was similar to the variation caused by the environment, potentially indicating that the environment caused little to no variation in the foraging efficiency. However, it is more likely that the effect of changing the environment is comparable to changing the initial memory.

When the standard deviations of the controls of the environment and initial memory are considered (table 2 and 3), the interpretation of the results differs from the statistical analysis. The differences between the summed DBH values when having varying memory sizes and retention intervals are smaller and might be non-existent, while the total food intake values do differ more than the standard deviation. The total food intake was much larger when the agent had a retention interval of 30 days and a memory size of 1000 or 1500 trees than when the agent had a retention interval of 60 or 356 days and a memory size of 1000 or 1500 trees. So, an effect of memory size and retention interval could potentially be found on the total food intake and not on the summed DBH, contrary to the statistical results. The current statistical results could be specific to the environment or initial memories. The somewhat large standard deviations indicate how sensitive the model is for different inputs or factors. This sensitivity is also apparent in the different results of the total food intake and summed DBH. When less food is present than the maximum potential production and when some memories are incorrect, no more statistically difference in foraging efficiency is found.

Because of the few simulations, the sensitivity of the model, and the contradictory statistical and descriptive results, it is difficult to determine the effect of memory capacity on the foraging efficiency. Therefore, the possibility that memory capacity did not influence the foraging efficiency should be considered. It could be argued that the memory content (quality) might be more important for efficient foraging than the memory capacity (quantity). The available memory space can be used more efficiently by only remembering the relevant details of food resources (instead of all information for all trees) and

by only remembering the relevant food resources (instead of remembering many food resources that lack detail). This is in line with earlier research. The more information is stored in the memory, the more chance on interference of memories (Kane and Engle, 2000). So, a larger memory might not be that beneficial. Additionally, research has shown that chimpanzees remember specific information about food resources that help them to forage for more high valued food resources (Sayers and Menzel, 2012; Janmaat et al., 2013a; Janmaat et al., 2013b; Ban et al., 2014; Janmaat et al., 2014; Ban et al., 2016). In the current model, the memory content was the same for every food resource. Which trees were forgotten, and thus remembered as well, was determined by the memory strength that only considered when the tree was last seen and whether food was present. So, the memory content was not tested within this model.

The results show a possible interaction between memory size and retention interval (figure 4), indicating that memory content might be indeed more important for foraging efficiency than memory capacity. When the agent had a short retention interval (30 days), it foraged more efficiently when it had a small memory (1000 items) compared to a large memory (2000 items), for all foraging efficiency measurements and even when the standard deviation was considered. The other way around, when the agent had a long retention interval (356 days), it foraged more efficiently when it had a large memory (2000 items) compared to a small memory (1000 items). This suggests a possible interaction between memory size and retention. The sample size was very small, so these results should be interpreted with caution. A smaller memory might be more beneficial when having a shorter retention interval because it avoids remembering irrelevant information and makes it possible to mainly remember recently visited trees. A larger memory might be more beneficial when having a longer retention interval because then the forager would be better in predicting the food presence, and then there will be more chance that high valued, often rare, trees are kept in the memory (Ban et al., 2016). In the current study, interactions could not be tested due to the lack of simulations. More research is necessary to investigate whether there is an interaction between memory size and retention.

However, it would be expected that memory content is only more important than the capacity if there was a limited capacity and, therefore, a trade-off between quality and quantity. The current model did not have a limited capacity, so an effect of capacity on foraging efficiency could still be expected. When more is remembered (by increasing both size and retention), the agent would be better in predicting where to go, regardless of the memories' quality. The agent knows more potential food resources and is thus better able to decide which direction to go. The lack of consistent significant results could have been due to the small sample size, but the model was also sensitive and other small factors could have caused the absence of an effect. Although the routes of the agent in the model are visually similar to the GPS tracks of chimpanzees in the wild, the average number of visited trees per day was much higher in the model (21.57) than observed in the wild (4.63; Janmaat et al., 2013a). This means that the current model is not simulating the natural forage behaviour. So, what factors in the current model could have influenced the results?

First of all, only one movement rule, the additive-gravity rule, was used for all simulations. Therefore, it is unknown whether the effects of the memory capacity on the foraging efficiency depend on the movement decisions of the additive-gravity rule. The additive-gravity rule was used because it provided frequent significant positive correlations between observed and predicted routes of primates (Janson, 2014). Additionally, the additive-gravity rule is cognitive less demanding than other potential movement rules and allows for updating the memory while foraging, unlike other movement rules (Janson, 2014). In the current model, the additive-gravity rule considered of each tree in the memory the DBH, distance, whether it was located in the core area, and food presence when determining which direction to go. However, the more trees are remembered and added to the additive-gravity rule, the more attractions in different directions, and the smaller the effect of these tree features. This could have influenced the foraging efficiency.

The model results do not confirm the added value of remembering the DBH to forage more efficiently. The memory size and retention interval had a similar effect on the summed DBH and the number of visited trees. For both foraging efficiency measurements, the agent foraged more efficiently when

having a retention interval of 30 days compared to having a retention interval of 60 days. If the DBH contributed to the foraging efficiency, it could be expected that the results for the summed DBH and number of visited trees differed. So based on the results of the study, it is unknown whether remembering the DBH is beneficial for navigating. However, previous studies have found that chimpanzees fed in and monitored larger trees (Janmaat et al., 2013a). The added value of remembering the DBH for the additive-gravity rule should be tested by doing several simulations with and without including the DBH in the additive-gravity rule. Other food resource features could be added and tested as well of which are known that chimpanzees use the information to forage. Such features are past feeding experiences (Ban et al., 2014), nutritional values (Ban et al., 2016), and the fruiting synchrony of trees from the same species (Janmaat et al., 2013b).

Another factor that could have influenced the results is the chosen range of memory sizes. The memory size for spatial information is challenging to measure and unknown for chimpanzees. A study on baboons (*Papio papio*) showed that they could remember a minimum of 3,500 – 5,000 picture-response associations (Fagot and Cook, 2006). However, the capacity for long-term visual information measured during a task might not represent the capacity of real-world spatial information (Kristjánsson and Draschkow, 2021). The agent visited much more trees in the ABM than chimpanzees observed in the wild. This could indicate that the memory sizes were too large. However, a smaller memory size than 1000 trees could not be tested because the trees in the memory would be depleted within the 10-day simulation. More simulations with a wider range of memory sizes are necessary to get a better understanding of the relationship between foraging efficiency and memory size. It is possible that the agent was too good at finding food. So, to make the model more realistic and to avoid the depletion of the memorised trees, some behavioural changes can be implemented, such as adding random walks, using sensory cues for foraging (instead of only memory), and not depleting the visited trees (e.g. by using nutritional values).

An absence of an effect of memory capacity on foraging efficiency might also be explained by how the retention interval was implemented in the model. The retention interval only affected the memory strength of each remembered tree. The longer ago the tree was seen, the weaker the memory. However, the retention interval did not change the process of forgetting. The tree with the weakest memory strength was the tree that would be forgotten. So, varying the retention interval did not influence the content of the memory and hence the foraging efficiency too. In a new or updated model, the retention should be implemented in a way that influences the memory content, the movement decisions, or how well the agent can predict the food availability.

Besides the described factors that could have influenced the results, it would be best to update the model even more to a more accurate and enhanced model. Although the environment is rather realistic (see appendix B), some properties of the complex rainforest environment could be added. Within tropical fruit tree species, 64% bears fruit synchronously (Chapman et al., 1999). Primates use this property to find fruit (Janmaat et al., 2012; Janmaat et al., 2013b), which could influence the foraging efficiency. The dispersion of trees from the same species could also be integrated into the model, for example, by using Moran's I. The exact locations of the trees were not used in the model to be able to test the influence of the environment on the foraging efficiency. Besides, it allows for controlled alterations in the environment for future research on foraging behaviour.

Furthermore, the nutritional values of the different food resources could be added. Research has shown that chimpanzees were more likely to change their travel direction for trees of fatty fruits (Ban et al., 2016), suggesting that chimpanzees remember and use this information during foraging. At last, the ABM environment could have a dynamic instead of a static environment. In the current model, the food did not grow back over time. By growing back food, the complicated food productions patterns of the rainforest can be recreated. Moreover, it allows for running simulations over the long term, which provides the opportunity to emerge the memory content. In the current model, an initial memory was created by taking a random sample of trees from the environment and randomly attribute when these were last seen. The foraging efficiency might be more accurate when the memory emerges from foraging using a movement rule and a set memory capacity.

Some propositions for changing the agent of the ABM are mentioned before, such as using different movement rules, expanding and testing the additive-gravity rule, extending the range of memory sizes, and remembering more food resource properties. In addition to these propositions, it would be interesting to add more agents to the ABM, considering the role of sociality on foraging efficiency. According to the social intelligence hypothesis, social complexity is the main selective force behind the evolution of enlarged brains, and consequently, intelligence (Jolly, 1966; Humphry, 1976). Research has shown that sociality has a positive impact on fitness (Silk et al., 2003), but how it affects fitness is still unknown (Thompson, 2019). By adding more agents to the models and social interactions, it would be possible to study both social and ecological effects on foraging efficiency.

Conclusion

The results of this study do not show an effect of memory capacity on the foraging efficiency of chimpanzees. It is possible that memory content is more important for efficient foraging than memory capacity. However, interpreting the results should be done with great caution because only a few simulations were run, and the model is sensitive to different inputs and factors. Hence it is still possible that memory capacity affects the foraging efficiency. More research is necessary to investigate how memory capacity, both size and retention, influences the foraging efficiency of chimpanzees. Many propositions are provided that could facilitate a more accurate model.

Since no effect of memory capacity is found on the foraging efficiency of chimpanzees, this study does not provide evidence for the ecological intelligence hypothesis. The ecological intelligence hypothesis states that factors of diet are the primary force shaping intelligent behaviour (Milton, 1981; Sol, 2009). Variation in cognitive skills used during foraging can be explained by the variation found in ecology (Rosati, 2017). Although the results of this study do not support the ecological intelligence hypothesis, there is already a large body of evidence from empirical research (Sol et al., 2005; Janmaat and Cancellor, 2010; Rosati, 2017), which emphasises the importance of more research. An important reason to create a model is to discover new questions and provide more insight into how the current knowledge and research is related to each other (Epstein, 2008). The ABM of this study can be used as a prototype for future research to get more insight into how memory capacity is related to foraging efficiency. There are many propositions discussed that can improve the model. Besides the more practical propositions, this study also showed the importance of getting a better understanding of the memory. For example, without understanding the mechanisms behind forgetting, it can be challenging to understand how memory capacity can be maintained.

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Appendix A: Model description

The description of the model follows the Overview, Design concepts, Detail (ODD) protocol (Grimm et al., 2006; Grimm et al., 2010).

1. Purpose

The aim of the model is to provide more insight into the role of memory during foraging of chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*) in the south of the Taï National Park, Côte d'Ivoire. The rainforest habitat of the chimpanzees is complex, especially when considering that the reproduction patterns of fruit trees vary widely (van Schaik et al., 1993; Janmaat et al., 2012) and that the majority of the diet of chimpanzees consists of fruit (Wrangham et al., 1998). Research has shown that chimpanzees use long-term spatial memory to relocate fruit-bearing trees (Janmaat et al., 2013). However, it is not clear yet how the memory capacity, including both its size (how many items can be remembered) and retention (how long items can be remembered), contributes to foraging efficiency. The foraging efficiency is here defined as the amount of food eaten (in meters, see explanation in 2. Entities, state variables, and scales) per meter travelled. This model will investigate this with a model experiment in which the memory sizes and retention intervals will be varied, and the foraging efficiency will be measured.

2. Entities, state variables, and scales

The entities of the Agent-Based Model (ABM) are a single chimpanzee (henceforth denoted as agent) and an artificially generated habitat, consisting of trees that vary in properties. The fruit, young leaves, or nuts that the trees can bear are the food resources for the agent. The traits of the agent are its location in the environment and its memory for the food resources. The memory is specified by the memory size, which determines how many food resources (trees) the agent can remember, and the retention interval, which determines how long the agent can keep a tree in the memory. The trees are characterised by their location and species. A tree can be located anywhere in the 26.5 km² range area of the agent, which equals the average territory size of the chimpanzees observed in the Taï rainforest (Janmaat et al., 2013). In the model environment, the length from north to south and from west to east is equal. The species determines for each tree the Diameter at Breast Height (DBH), food index, and Maximum Detection Distance (MDD). The DBH is an accurate measurement for the food production of trees (McFarland Symington, 1988; Chapman et al., 1992). The larger the DBH, the more fruit and above-ground biomass, but the exact relationship between DBH (in meters) and fruit or other food biomass (in kilograms) varies depending on factors that are not included in the model or unknown (Ngomanda et al., 2013; Ouédraogo et al., 2020). Hence, DBH in meters is used as an indicator of the potential food production of a tree and not converted to biomass (kg). The food index determines how much food of the potential production is present, and thus available for the agent to consume. The food index ranks 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 corresponded to 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% of the potential food production. The distance from which a tree can be noticed by the agent is the MDD of the tree. The distance that determines whether it is considered as eating from the tree is specified by the minimal tree distance. The minimal tree distance is not determined by the species of the tree, but equal for all trees.

Each tree in the memory of the agent has a certain attraction from the agent towards the tree, which influences the direction in which the agent moves. This attraction is determined by the distance between the agent and the tree, the DBH, and whether food is present in the tree. The attraction towards the tree is also affected by the location of the tree. In the centre of the range area is the core area of 17.8 km² located (Janmaat et al., 2013). Trees in the core area have a larger attraction than trees in the periphery to keep the agent within the range area (the core attraction). When there are no trees in the memory that the agent can be attracted to, the agent will move in a random direction. The maximal turning angle relative to the preceding direction during this random walk is determined by the maximal turn.

Chimpanzees travel on average 2.4 km per day (Doran, 1997; Bates and Byrne, 2009). The total run time of one simulation is ten days, so the agent travels 24 km during each simulation. Since the agent travels 2 m (step length) during each time unit (tick), one simulation takes 12000 ticks. Because speed is homogenous in this model, a tick represents both a temporal unit and a spatial unit. See table A1 for all variables and parameters used in the model.

Table A1. The parameters and variables used in the Agent-Based Model. For each parameter (in bold) or variable a definition is given together with the units and values used in the model. The parameters and variables can be divided into three categories: those that describe the individual, those that describe the trees and those that determine the movement.

	Parameters and variables	Definition	Units	Value
<i>Agent</i>	Location	The x and y coordinates of the agent	m	[0, 5148]
	Memory size	Number of trees that the agent can store in the memory		1000, 1500, 2000
	Retention interval	How long the memory of a tree can be stored in the memory	m	36000, 72000, 427200
<i>Tree</i>	Location	The x and y coordinates of the tree	m	[0, 5148]
	Species	The species the tree belongs to		
	DBH	The Diameter of Breast Height of the tree trunk	m	
	MDD	Maximum Detection Distance of the tree	m	
	Food index	The percentage of the maximal food production that is present		0, 1, 2, 3, 4
	Minimal tree distance	Distance from tree that determines when it is considered as eating from a tree	m	2
	<i>Movement</i>	Total ticks	Number of steps taken during one simulation	
Step length		Length of each step	m	2
Core attraction		How much stronger the magnitude of the attraction towards the tree is because of its location in the periphery or core area		0, 0.5
Maximal turn		Maximal turning angle relative to the preceding direction when random walking	degrees	40

3. Process overview and scheduling

Before the model is run, it is provided with an environment of varying trees with properties that remain static during the course of the simulation. An initial memory of the agent is created by taking a random sample of trees from the environment and storing the traits of these (location, DBH, whether food is present, and how long ago seen). The sample size is determined by the memory size. Then the basic sequence of the model starts. First, the agent looks around. If the agent is within the MDD of a tree, it will notice the tree and save the tree in its memory. When the memory is full (the number of trees stored in the memory is equal to the memory size), then a tree must be forgotten first. To determine which tree should be forgotten the memory strength of each tree in the memory is calculated. The tree with the weakest memory strength will be forgotten. When all new trees are stored in the memory, it is checked whether there are trees in the memory that have been last seen beyond the length of the retention interval. If so, those trees will be forgotten. After that, it is checked whether the agent is within the minimal tree distance of the nearest tree. If so, the agent will eat all food that is available from this tree. At last, a new walking direction is calculated, and the agent moves a step length in that direction. Then the sequence starts again. A flowchart visualisation of the process overview is shown in figure A1.

4. Design concepts

Emergence. The route of the agent in the model environment emerges from a combination of memory rules and decision rules during foraging. The foraging efficiency depends on the routes the agent takes and hence is emergent too.

Figure A1. Flowchart of the Agent-Based Model. The yellow parallelograms represent input variables and data frames and output data frames.

Observation. During each tick, the position (x and y coordinates) of the agent is stored. If the agent is within the minimal tree distance, the DBH of that tree and the food intake are stored as well. The food intake is the total amount of food available at the tree, which is determined by the DBH and food index.

Sensing. To navigate through the environment, the agent knows the exact location and DBH of all trees in the memory and implicitly knows its own location. A tree is added to the memory when the agent is within the MDD. Additionally, the agent knows whether food is present, but not the exact amount of food. In the initial memory, there is an accuracy of 61% of whether food is present, similar to real measurements (from behavioural data of Janmaat et al., 2013). However, when the agent is within the MDD, it will correctly see and store whether food is present.

Fitness. The additive-gravity rule is used for foraging towards larger food resources (Janson, 2014) and thus increase the fitness of the agent. It determines in which direction the agent will travel during each tick. The additive-gravity rule takes the DBH of all possible goals and the distance between the agent and all possible goals into account when calculating the direction (see figure 2 in main text). Possible goals are all trees in the memory that have food present. This way, the agent will be directed to trees have more food and are closer by, increasing the foraging efficiency. Furthermore, in order to add a tree to the memory, the memory strength of each tree in the memory is calculated to establish the order by which trees will be forgotten. Trees that do not have food and have been unseen for the longest period will be forgotten first. The longer a tree stays in the memory, the higher the chance on interference (Kane and Engle, 2000) and the higher chance that this resource has already disappeared. Hence, revisiting resources seen long ago is a greater risk of losing time and energy by going somewhere wrong. By using the memory strength to determine which tree should be forgotten, the available memory space will be used efficiently.

Prediction. Because the additive-gravity rule is used to navigate through the environment, the agent does not have one specific goal tree in mind. Instead, all trees in the memory that have food are possible goals. Despite that the initial memory of whether food is present is 61% accurate, the agent still predicts the direction towards trees that have potentially more food and are closer by to forage more efficiently.

Stochasticity. The placement and characteristics (DBH, food index, and MDD) of the trees are randomly assigned but kept identical for all simulations when testing the effect of the memory capacity on the foraging efficiency of the agent. The random sample of trees in the initial memory does differ for each simulation together with the ticks when the tree was last seen (being within the MDD). At last, when the agent does not have trees in the memory to which it can be attracted by the additive-gravity rule, the agent travels in a random direction. This happens when all trees in the memory are recently visited and do not have food anymore, so the additive gravity rule does not have any goals left to direct to.

5. Initialisation

The trees in the model environment belong to the following species: *Azelia bella*, *Dacryodes klaineana*, *Dialium aubrevillei*, *Irvingia grandifolia*, *Klainedoxa gabonensis*, *Nauclea diderrichii*, *Panda oleosa*, *Parinari excelsa*, *Pouteria aningeri*, *Sacoglottis gabonensis*, *Sterculia oblonga*, *Treculia Africana*, *Trichoscypha arborea*, *Xylia evansii*, and *Zanha golungensis*. These species form the majority of the fruit species eaten by chimpanzees and include abundant and rare species (Normand, 2009). The DBH, MDD and food index are assigned to the individual trees using distributions similar to the observational data (see 6. Input data and Appendix B). Trees are randomly placed in the model environment, taking the DBH into account to avoid unrealistically small distances or even spatial overlap between trees. The number of trees of a species in the environment depends on the density of the tree species.

The initial memory of the agent consists of a set of random trees from the environment. The amount of trees depends on the memory size. The memory size was set to 1000, 1500 or 2000 depending which memory capacity is tested. The retention interval determines how long ago the tree was last seen, ranging from 1 to the set retention interval. The retention interval is set to one month (30 days), two months (60

days) or one year (356 days). Research suggests that chimpanzees can remember food resources for one month and up to three years (Normand et al., 2009; Janmaat et al., 2013). In the initial memory it is also stored whether food is present at a tree. Because behavioural data from Janmaat et al. (2013) showed that 61% of the goal-directed food resources have food, an accuracy of 61% was used.

The starting location of the agent is always in the centre of the model environment. The step length of the agent is 2 m, and therefore, the minimal tree distance as well. The total distance travelled is kept constant for all simulations. When plotting the distance travelled against the foraging efficiency, it is visible how the efficiency first is unstable and then gets more stable between 20 km and 30 km travelled (figure A2). After 50 km travelled, the foraging efficiency drops even more, which is due to the declining number of food resources. Food does not grow back in the model. So, to get reliable results, a total distance was set to 24 km, in between the unstable and declining period. A chimpanzee travels 2.4 km in one day on average (Doran, 1997; Bates and Byrne, 2009), so 24 km is equal to 10 days of walking and 12,000 ticks.

Figure A2. The effect of distance travelled on the foraging efficiency in the Agent-Based Model of foraging chimpanzees. The distance travelled is in meters and the forage efficiency is measured in the amount of food (in meters) eaten per meter travelled.

6. Input data

The DBH, MDD, and density data are derived from a long-term observational study from 2009 until 2011 in the Taï National Park, Côte d'Ivoire, see the supplementary materials of Janmaat et al. (2013) for data processing. Additional density data is derived from Goné Bi (2007). These data sets are used to derive the descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum) of the DBH and MDD of each species, which were subsequently used to generate the model environment. The data set of Janmaat et al. (2013) also included behavioural data about which part of the tree was most often eaten.

Data of the food index is derived from phenological data from 1997 until 2011 in the Taï National Park (Anderson et al., 2005; Janmaat et al., 2013). The food index was recorded for nuts, ripe and unripe fruit, young and old leaves, and flower bud and blossoming flowers. Which measurement is used depends on which part of the tree was eaten the most of each species. The probability distributions of the food index ranks are used to generate the model environment. A detailed description of how the input data was used to generate the model environment can be found in Appendix B.

7. Submodels

Environment. All trees in the 26.5 km² model environment are described by five key variables: food index, DBH, MDD, density, and location. The values of these variables depend on the species the tree belongs to. There are two main steps in creating the environment. The first step is to determine the probability distributions and descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum) of the key variables for each species using observational data from the Taï National Park, Côte d'Ivoire (see 6. Input data). The second step is to apply these distributions or parameters to generate random samples of each key variable of each species. The size of these samples depends on the number of trees of each species in the model environment, which is calculated by using the density. Each tree from a certain species is randomly assigned a food index, DBH, MDD, and location (x and y coordinates) from the samples. A detailed description of how the model environment is created can be found in Appendix B.

The DBH and food index are used to calculate the amount of food available at each modelled tree by using the following formula:

$$food\ available = \left(\frac{food\ index}{4} \right) * DBH$$

in which the food index is an ordinal variable ranging from 0 to 4 and the DBH a continuous variable in meters. The DBH represents the potential food production of a tree (McFarland Symington, 1988; Chapman et al., 1992). Because the exact relationship between DBH (in m) and the biomass of fruit, nuts or young leaves (in kg) is unknown (Ngomanda et al., 2014; Ouédraogo et al., 2020), the DBH is not converted to biomass. Hence the food available is expressed in meters as well. By using this formula, it is assumed that of trees with food index 0 have no food present; that of trees with index 1 have 25% of their potential food production present; that of trees with index 2 have 50% of their potential food production present; that of trees with index 3 have 75% of their potential food production present; that of trees with index 4 have all of their potential food production present.

Movement. Before the model is run, the initial memory is created (see 5. Initialisation). Then the sequence starts, which will be repeated for each tick during one simulation. First, the distance between the agent and the surrounding trees is calculated. The surrounding trees are the trees that are closer to the individual than the maximum MDD in the data set. For all surrounding trees, it is checked whether the agent is within the MDD of that tree. If that is the case and the tree is not in the memory yet, the tree will be stored in the memory. If there are fewer trees in the memory than the memory size, the tree is simply added to the memory. Otherwise, another tree must be forgotten first to create memory space. To determine which tree will be forgotten the memory strength of all trees in the memory is calculated using the following formula:

$$memory\ strength = \frac{2 + food\ present}{current\ tick - tick\ when\ last\ seen}$$

Food present is a binary parameter, so by adding 2 to food present, memories of trees that are expected to have food will be 1.5 times stronger than memories of trees that are not expected to have food. Memory strength is also determined by the amount of time that went by since the tree was last seen, which is the difference between the current tick and the tick when last seen. The tree with the lowest memory strength will be replaced with the tree that is seen by the agent. After having seen the tree, and stored when necessary, the information in the memory about the tree is updated. Tick when last seen will be set to the current tick, and food present will be set to 1 if food is available and to 0 if no food is available.

Then for all the trees in the memory is checked whether they are seen longer ago than the retention interval and deleted if true. From the trees left in the memory, it is checked whether the agent is within the minimal tree distance of the nearest tree. If so, the agent will visit the tree. All available food will be eaten (set to 0) and stored for analysis, together with the DBH of that tree.

After that, the additive-gravity rule is applied to determine the travel direction of the agent. For each tree in the memory that is expected to have food, an attraction vector is calculated. The direction of this vector points from the location of the agent to the location of the tree. The DBH and distance determine the length of the vector, which represents the magnitude of the attraction towards the tree:

$$attraction = \frac{DBH}{distance} * (1 + core\ attraction)$$

The larger the DBH (m), the stronger the attraction and the larger the distance (m), the smaller the attraction. Trees that are located in the core area are 1.5 times more attractive than three in the periphery of the territory because the core attraction is 0 for trees in the periphery and 0.5 for trees in the core area. The summed vector will point into the travel direction of the agent, see figure 2 in the main text. If the summed vector has a length of 0, the agent will travel in a random direction between 40 degrees to the left or right (maximal turn). After the direction is calculated or determined, the agent travels 2 m in that direction, and the new location will be determined. Then the sequence starts again until 12000 ticks went by.

8. References

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Appendix B: Model environment

This appendix is written in collaboration with Ross Settle (Settle, 2020).

The model environment created for this study models the natural environment of the Tai chimpanzees as closely as possible. The model environment consists of trees from fifteen different species, representing both common food sources of high abundance and rare foods (Normand, 2009). The total area of the model environment was 26.5 km², which equals the average territory size of chimpanzees observed in the Tai National Park rainforest, Côte d'Ivoire, with a core area of 17.8 km² located in the centre (Janmaat et al., 2013). The length from north to south and from east to west was equal in the model environment. All trees are described by five key variables: food index, Maximum Detection Distance (MDD), Diameter at Breast Height (DBH), density, and location. There are two main steps in creating the model environment: (1) determine probability distributions or descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum) of the key variables of each tree species based on observational data in Tai National Park rainforest, Côte d'Ivoire, and (2) apply these distributions or parameters to generate random samples of each key variable of each species.

The food index was derived from phenological data on 110 species and 3,480 trees recorded from 1997 until 2011 (Anderson et al., 2005; Janmaat et al., 2013). It was measured for different food types using a scale ranging from 0% to 100% of the crown containing food (see table B1). Since chimpanzees predominantly eat fruit (Wrangham et al., 1998), the food index of fruit was used as a default. If another food type of a species was eaten more frequently, based on observational data on chimpanzee behaviour and phenological data of their visited trees from 2009 to 2011 (Janmaat et al., 2013), then the food index of that food type was used. For each species, the proportion that each food index level occurred was calculated and used as probabilities to generate a random sample of food index levels for that species.

Table B1. Food index values and the corresponding percentage of the crown containing food.

Index	Percentage of crown
0	0%
1	1 – 25%
2	26 – 50%
3	51 – 75%
4	76 – 100%

The chimpanzee behaviour and phenological data also included the MDD of the visited trees. For each visited tree, the visual detection distance of the tree crown and trunk and the olfactory detection distance was measured. The maximum value represented the MDD of that tree. The mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum MDD was calculated for each species. For some species, no MDD was available. In those cases, the average mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum of the other species were used. The mean and standard deviation were used to generate a random sample of MDD values for each species. Values in the random sample smaller than the minimum were set to the minimum MDD of that species and values greater than the maximum were set to the maximum MDD.

A botanical map containing data of 17 species and 15,876 individual trees within the core area of the chimpanzee's territory (Janmaat et al., 2013) contained DBH data of the trees. The DBH distributions were skewed, requiring an inverse-transformation to render it symmetric. So, this transform was applied, after which the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum DBH of each species was determined. These were used to generate a random sample of DBH values for each species, using the same method as for the MDD values. These random samples were then transformed back by doing an inverse-transformation again.

The density was derived from the botanical map as well (Janmaat et al., 2013). However, of some species, the density data was not available. For those species, the density was derived from observational data from Goné Bi (2007). The density was used to determine the number of trees of each species in the model environment. To assign each tree a random location, x and y coordinates were generated randomly using a uniform distribution and setting the minimum and maximum to the boundaries of the environment. The DBH was taken into account when placing the tree to avoid overlap with unrealistically small distances or even spatial overlap between trees. Not all trees fitted in the environment, so the residual trees were placed randomly without taking the DBH into account. See table B2 for probability distributions or descriptive statistics of key variables of each tree species in the model environment.

Table B2. Probability distributions or descriptive statistics of key variables of each tree species in the model environment. For each tree species is shown which food type is eaten the most by chimpanzees, the mean \pm SD DBH, the mean \pm SD MDD, the density and the proportion that each food index was present. * DBH mean and SD are of transformed data. **MDD data was absent, so the average mean and SD was used.

Species	Food type	DBH* mean \pm SD	MDD mean \pm SD	Density trees/ha	Food index proportions				
					0	1	2	3	4
<i>Afzelia bella</i>	Young leaves	1.13 \pm 0.28	30.54 \pm 6.64**	0.036	0.7487	0.1825	0.0447	0.0206	0.0036
<i>Dacryodes klaineana</i>	Ripe fruit	1.94 \pm 0.37	30.54 \pm 6.64**	0.193	0.9278	0.0436	0.0216	0.0030	0.0040
<i>Dialium aubrevillei</i>	Ripe fruit	1.57 \pm 0.41	23.35 \pm 5.56	0.842	0.8517	0.0769	0.0463	0.0125	0.0125
<i>Irvingia grandifolia</i>	Ripe fruit	1.10 \pm 0.29	32.21 \pm 7.11	0.068	0.8960	0.0603	0.0270	0.0125	0.0042
<i>Klainedoxa gabonensis</i>	Ripe fruit	0.92 \pm 0.23	34.70 \pm 6.43	0.418	0.7489	0.1712	0.0588	0.0159	0.0052
<i>Nauclea diderrichii</i>	Ripe fruit	1.22 \pm 0.33	27.95 \pm 7.45	0.441	0.8874	0.0469	0.0369	0.0213	0.0075
<i>Panda oleosa</i>	Ripe fruit	2.63 \pm 0.85	23.26 \pm 5.94	0.717	0.9224	0.0558	0.0150	0.0050	0.0018
<i>Parinari excelsa</i>	Ripe fruit	0.97 \pm 0.24	35.22 \pm 8.79	0.368	0.8225	0.0637	0.0743	0.0273	0.0121
<i>Pouteria aningeri</i>	Ripe fruit	1.04 \pm 0.27	30.54 \pm 6.64**	0.083	0.9624	0.0103	0.0160	0.0085	0.0028
<i>Sacoglottis gabonensis</i>	Ripe fruit	1.13 \pm 0.43	36.56 \pm 6.68	1.084	0.7807	0.1195	0.0763	0.0221	0.0014
<i>Sterculia oblonga</i>	Ripe fruit	1.54 \pm 0.47	33.07 \pm 5.74	0.369	0.9517	0.0391	0.0082	0.0011	0
<i>Treulia Africana</i>	Ripe fruit	1.41 \pm 0.44	23.31 \pm 8.14	0.045	0.9410	0.0304	0.0228	0.0057	0
<i>Trichoscypha arborea</i>	Young leaves	2.94 \pm 0.85	30.54 \pm 6.64**	0.518	0.5753	0.4002	0.0164	0.0028	0.0051
<i>Xylia evansii</i>	Ripe fruit	1.48 \pm 0.47	25.87 \pm 8.29	2.193	0.8486	0.1031	0.0348	0.0107	0.0028
<i>Zanha golungensis</i>	Ripe fruit	0.71 \pm 0.24	40.44 \pm 2.88	0.198	0.9700	0.0150	0.0104	0.0039	0.0007

Previous work has linked higher fruit production to larger DBHs (Janmaat et al., 2013). However, to this studies knowledge, no work has linked DBH to MDD. Linear regression found no correlation within species. Results are shown in table B3 and figure B1. Several species had large R-squared values, but they also typically had very few observations. For this reason, this study chose not to link DBH and MDD.

Table B3. Linear regression between DBH and MDD. Not all species from the model environment are included, because of these species there was no data available of the MDD.

Species	Slope	R-squared
<i>Dialium aubrevillei</i>	-0.07824	0.045017
<i>Irvingia grandifoli</i>	0.04278	0.038854
<i>Klainedoxa gabonensis</i>	0.02359	0.016954
<i>Nauclea diderrichii</i>	-0.02288	0.007885
<i>Panda oleosa</i>	0.1657	0.026209
<i>Parinari excelsa</i>	0.15523	0.389571
<i>Sacoglottis gabonensis</i>	-0.0013	0.000062
<i>Sterculia oblonga</i>	-0.0762	0.236811
<i>Treulia africana</i>	0.11331	0.201126
<i>Zanha golungensis</i>	0.37255	0.56975

Figure B1. Linear regression between DBH and MDD. Not all species from the model environment are included, because of these species there was no data available of the MDD.

To check for accuracy of the model environment, this study visually compared the cumulative distribution of DBH and MDD along with the proportion of the food index for each species. The proportions of the metrics appeared to be similar (figure B2), so the model environment was deemed accurate.

Figure B2. Comparison between observational data and data of the model environment of the key variables DBH, MDD, and food index. Yellow represents data of the model environment and green of the observed environment. Figures on the left (A, C, E) compare data of *Dialium aubreville* and figures on the right (B, D, F) compare data of *Nauclea diderrichii*. A-B show the cumulative distributions of the DBH. C-D show the cumulative distributions of the MDD. E-F show the proportion of the food index levels.

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